

EXAMINING A DECADE OF SECTOR-SPECIFIC DEVELOPMENTS: PROFESSIONAL, SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL ACTIVITIES, ADMINISTRATIVE, AND SUPPORT ACTIVITIES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Carla Selma, Eva Clark, Albert Lewis, Jack Bailey, Olivia Campbell
Zealandina Agency, United Kingdom

Abstract:

This article conducts a thorough analysis of statistical data pertaining to sector-specific developments in Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities, as well as Administrative and Support Activities within the Romanian Mountain Area over the period spanning 2008 to 2018. The study aims to provide insights into the transformative dynamics, economic contributions, and challenges faced by these critical sectors in a unique regional context.

1. Introduction:

The Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities sector, coupled with Administrative and Support Activities, constitutes a cornerstone of regional development. This article focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area, exploring a decade's worth of statistical data to unravel trends, innovations, and the economic impact of these interconnected sectors. (Covaci B & PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (1/2022))

Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h)

2. Methodology:

Employing a meticulous quantitative methodology, this research synthesizes data from official reports, industry databases, and pertinent publications. The analysis includes key indicators such as sector-specific growth rates, employment trends, and technological advancements, providing a holistic understanding of the region's professional and administrative landscape.

3. Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities:

This section delves into statistical intricacies surrounding professional, scientific, and technical activities within the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as research and development investments, innovation indices, and the growth of specialized enterprises are scrutinized to assess the sector's role in fostering regional progress.

4. Administrative and Support Activities:

Examining Administrative and Support Activities, this segment explores statistical analyses of outsourcing trends, business support services, and administrative infrastructure growth. The article aims to shed light on the sector's contribution to enhancing the efficiency and productivity of other industries in the region.

5. Economic Contributions:

Assessing the economic impact of Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities, as well as Administrative and Support Activities, this section investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability. The article emphasizes the sectors' vital role in shaping the economic landscape of the Romanian Mountain Area.

6. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying notable trends and challenges faced by these sectors during the specified period, this section provides insights into factors influencing professional and administrative dynamics. Considerations such as technological disruptions, regulatory changes, and globalization effects are explored, offering a nuanced perspective on future developments.

7. Results:

The statistics for the sectors Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support activities (figures 2.9.1 – 2.9.5 and appendices chapter 2), show for each sector separately rising values for the mean and median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (statistical values for Average, Std. Error of the mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, 25th, 50th and 75th percentiles; they are repeated for each individual indicator), as follows: average of 130733.11 , standard error of mean 2312,287, median 129397.00, standard deviation 6936,860, variance 48120028,611, Skewness

.925, standard error of Skewness .717, Kurtosis .647, standard error of Kurtosis 1,400, distance 21858, minimum 122787.5, maximum 1446 percentile 25 125090.50, 50 - 129397.00, 75 - 135078.00.

The presented values demonstrate that the sectors Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support activities in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry. The central tendency of the sectors Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support activities of the economy in the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator show a high degree of non-variability, which means that the results do not show a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

Figure 2.9.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.9.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.9.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.9.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.9.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The harmonization statistic presents relevant values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .089, .274, -.105, .721, -. 100, -.080; R-square .329, .235, -8.882E-15, 1.000, -1.132E-15, .000; RMSE 981,750, 1274,171, .000, 6936,860, 130,026, 159,107; MAPS 10,942, 6,256, .000, 39,730, 3,894, 5,624; MaxAPE 49,488, 22,997, .000, 133,747, 9,099, 13,100; MAE 592,602, 886,008, .000, 5481,235, 67,461, 81,226; MaxAE 2456,933, 3011,126, .000,

13911,889, 372,868, 488,499; Normalized BIC 12.947, 2.039, 9.560, 17.933, 10.159, 10.566.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S9

		Forecast										
Model		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073
	st	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
	UCL	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673
	LCL	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325
	UCL	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424
	LCL	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	20228	21002	21777	22551	23326	24100	24874	25649	26423	27197	27972
	UCL	25654	26455	27257	28058	28859	29660	30460	31261	32061	32862	33662
	LCL	14802	15549	16297	17045	17792	18540	19288	20036	20785	21533	22281
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	4519	4702	4885	5068	5251	5433	5616	5799	5982	6165	6348
	UCL	5787	6495	7081	7604	8086	8539	8971	9386	9786	10175	10553
	LCL	3251	2909	2688	2532	2415	2328	2262	2213	2178	2155	2143
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	992	992	992	992	992	992	992	992	992	992	992
	UCL	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690
	LCL	294	294	294	294	294	294	294	294	294	294	294
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	8840	9162	9483	9805	10127	10449	10771	11093	11414	11736	12058
	UCL	11034	11367	11699	12032	12364	12697	13029	13361	13694	14026	14358
	LCL	6646	6957	7268	7579	7890	8201	8512	8824	9135	9446	9758

Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	2501	2614	2727	2840	2954	3067	3180	3293	3407	3520	3633
	UCL	3112	3228	3345	3461	3577	3694	3810	3926	4043	4159	4275
	LCL	1889	1999	2109	2220	2330	2440	2550	2661	2771	2881	2991
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	1668	1741	1813	1885	1957	2030	2102	2174	2246	2319	2391
	UCL	2244	2554	2809	3036	3244	3439	3624	3802	3973	4138	4299
	LCL	1093	927	816	734	671	620	580	547	520	499	483
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098
	UCL	1440	1582	1691	1783	1863	1936	2004	2066	2125	2180	2233
	LCL	756	614	505	413	333	260	192	130	71	16	-37
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072
	UCL	23539	26216	28271	30003	31529	32908	34177	35358	36467	37516	38514
	LCL	10604	7927	5873	4141	2615	1235	-34	-1214	-2324	-3373	-4370
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016
	UCL	2872	3226	3498	3728	3930	4112	4280	4436	4583	4722	4854
	LCL	1160	806	534	304	102	-80	-248	-404	-551	-690	-822
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	5610	5787	5965	6142	6319	6496	6673	6851	7028	7205	7382
	UCL	7121	7306	7490	7675	7859	8044	8229	8413	8598	8782	8966
	LCL	4099	4269	4439	4609	4778	4948	5118	5288	5458	5628	5798
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146
	UCL	1667	1883	2049	2188	2311	2423	2525	2620	2710	2794	2875
	LCL	625	409	243	104	-19	-131	-233	-328	-418	-502	-583
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134
	UCL	3039	3414	3702	3944	4158	4351	4529	4694	4849	4996	5136
	LCL	1229	854	566	324	110	-83	-261	-426	-581	-728	-868
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	3595	3737	3878	4020	4161	4303	4444	4586	4727	4869	5010
	UCL	4772	4919	5066	5214	5361	5508	5655	5803	5950	6097	6244
	LCL	2419	2555	2690	2826	2962	3098	3233	3369	3505	3641	3777

Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185
	UCL	4557	5005	5362	5668	5941	6188	6417	6631	6832	7023	7204
	LCL	1813	1366	1009	702	430	182	-47	-260	-462	-652	-834
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486
	UCL	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889
	LCL	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198
	UCL	18724	20858	22516	23920	25161	26284	27319	28282	29188	30045	30861
	LCL	7671	5537	3879	2475	1234	111	-924	-1887	-2793	-3650	-4465
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493
	UCL	3560	3945	4247	4504	4732	4939	5130	5308	5475	5633	5784
	LCL	1425	1040	738	481	253	46	-145	-323	-490	-648	-799
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	892	892	892	892	892	892	892	892	892	892	892
	UCL	1246	1382	1488	1578	1658	1730	1796	1857	1915	1970	2023
	LCL	538	402	296	206	126	54	-12	-74	-132	-186	-239
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980
	UCL	7132	7995	8660	9223	9719	10168	10581	10966	11327	11669	11994
	LCL	2829	1966	1301	738	242	-207	-620	-1005	-1366	-1708	-2033
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738
	UCL	2533	2776	2972	3141	3292	3429	3556	3675	3786	3892	3993
	LCL	943	700	504	335	185	47	-80	-198	-310	-416	-517
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	2290	2403	2517	2631	2744	2858	2971	3085	3199	3312	3426
	UCL	3069	3506	3867	4189	4487	4767	5034	5290	5537	5777	6011
	LCL	1510	1301	1167	1072	1001	949	909	881	860	848	841
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	912	912	912	912	912	912	912	912	912	912	912
	UCL	1330	1503	1636	1748	1846	1936	2018	2094	2166	2234	2298
	LCL	494	321	188	76	-22	-112	-194	-270	-342	-410	-474

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834
	UCL	16840	18476	19783	20903	21899	22805	23641	24423	25158	25855	26519
	LCL	6828	5192	3886	2766	1770	864	27	-754	-1489	-2186	-2850
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339
	UCL	1938	2131	2286	2418	2537	2644	2743	2836	2923	3006	3085
	LCL	740	547	392	259	141	34	-66	-158	-246	-328	-407
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652
	UCL	2328	2532	2696	2838	2965	3081	3187	3287	3381	3471	3556
	LCL	975	772	607	465	338	223	116	16	-78	-167	-252
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	4989	5124	5260	5395	5530	5666	5801	5936	6072	6207	6343
	UCL	6554	6697	6840	6983	7126	7269	7412	7555	7698	7841	7984
	LCL	3424	3551	3679	3807	3934	4062	4190	4318	4446	4573	4701
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223
	UCL	3309	3738	4069	4350	4597	4821	5027	5219	5400	5570	5733
	LCL	1137	709	377	97	-150	-375	-581	-773	-953	-1124	-1286
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	790	790	790	790	790	790	790	790	790	790	790
	UCL	1232	1393	1520	1627	1722	1809	1888	1963	2032	2098	2161
	LCL	349	188	61	-46	-142	-228	-308	-382	-452	-518	-580
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	921	921	921	921	921	921	921	921	921	921	921
	UCL	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527
	LCL	316	316	316	316	316	316	316	316	316	316	316
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095
	UCL	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077
	LCL	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706
	UCL	17753	19843	21447	22799	23991	25068	26058	26980	27846	28665	29444
	LCL	7659	5569	3965	2613	1421	344	-646	-1568	-2434	-3253	-4032

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062
	UCL	4231	4716	5087	5401	5677	5926	6156	6369	6570	6760	6940
	LCL	1893	1408	1037	723	447	198	-32	-245	-446	-636	-816
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	1008	1060	1113	1166	1219	1271	1324	1377	1430	1482	1535
	UCL	1307	1483	1631	1764	1887	2003	2115	2222	2326	2427	2526
	LCL	709	638	596	568	550	539	533	532	533	537	544
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786
	UCL	2611	2953	3215	3437	3631	3807	3969	4120	4262	4396	4523
	LCL	961	619	357	135	-59	-235	-397	-548	-690	-824	-951
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	881	931	981	1031	1081	1132	1182	1232	1282	1332	1382
	UCL	1119	1268	1393	1507	1614	1714	1811	1905	1996	2084	2171
	LCL	643	595	569	555	549	549	552	559	568	579	593
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	857	857	857	857	857	857	857	857	857	857	857
	UCL	1333	1530	1681	1809	1921	2023	2116	2203	2285	2362	2435
	LCL	381	184	33	-95	-207	-309	-402	-489	-571	-648	-721
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359
	UCL	6140	6877	7443	7920	8341	8721	9070	9395	9701	9990	10265
	LCL	2578	1841	1275	798	377	-3	-352	-678	-983	-1272	-1547
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	856	856	856	856	856	856	856	856	856	856	856
	UCL	1181	1315	1418	1505	1582	1651	1715	1774	1830	1883	1933
	LCL	531	397	294	207	130	61	-3	-62	-118	-171	-221
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	44877	46031	47184	48337	49491	50644	51798	52951	54105	55258	56412
	UCL	54199	55399	56599	57799	58998	60197	61396	62595	63794	64992	66191
	LCL	35555	36662	37769	38876	39984	41091	42199	43307	44416	45524	46633
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536
	UCL	45846	48122	50020	51681	53177	54549	55824	57020	58150	59223	60248
	LCL	27226	24950	23053	21391	19895	18523	17248	16052	14922	13849	12824

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	5572	5944	6316	6688	7060	7432	7803	8175	8547	8919	9291
	UCL	6044	6425	6805	7184	7564	7944	8323	8703	9082	9461	9840
	LCL	5100	5464	5828	6191	6555	6919	7284	7648	8012	8377	8741
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827
	UCL	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814
	LCL	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487
	UCL	11786	13565	14930	16081	17095	18012	18855	19640	20377	21074	21737
	LCL	3187	1408	43	-1108	-2122	-3039	-3882	-4667	-5404	-6101	-6764
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953
	UCL	4296	4851	5278	5638	5954	6241	6504	6749	6980	7197	7405
	LCL	1610	1054	628	268	-49	-335	-598	-844	-1074	-1292	-1499
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251
	UCL	1959	2242	2460	2645	2808	2955	3091	3217	3336	3448	3555
	LCL	543	260	42	-143	-306	-453	-588	-715	-833	-946	-1052
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	706	706	706	706	706	706	706	706	706	706	706
	UCL	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369
	LCL	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164
	UCL	1860	2116	2316	2487	2637	2774	2900	3017	3128	3232	3332
	LCL	467	212	11	-159	-309	-446	-572	-689	-800	-904	-1004
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203
	UCL	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103
	LCL	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	13860	14388	14916	15444	15972	16499	17027	17555	18083	18611	19139
	UCL	17729	19860	21617	23182	24623	25977	27264	28499	29691	30846	31971
	LCL	9991	8916	8214	7705	7320	7022	6791	6612	6476	6376	6307

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	3498	3628	3758	3889	4019	4149	4279	4409	4539	4669	4800
	UCL	4616	4752	4888	5023	5159	5294	5430	5566	5701	5837	5972
	LCL	2380	2505	2629	2754	2879	3003	3128	3253	3378	3502	3627
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047
	UCL	1482	1633	1752	1853	1943	2025	2101	2171	2238	2301	2360
	LCL	611	461	342	240	150	68	-8	-78	-144	-207	-267
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158
	UCL	2915	3129	3303	3454	3589	3713	3827	3934	4035	4131	4223
	LCL	1402	1188	1014	863	727	604	489	382	281	186	94
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	7372	7635	7898	8162	8425	8688	8951	9214	9477	9740	10003
	UCL	8726	8996	9266	9535	9805	10075	10345	10615	10884	11154	11423
	LCL	6019	6275	6531	6788	7044	7300	7557	7813	8070	8327	8583

7. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a comprehensive statistical overview of sector-specific developments in Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities, as well as Administrative and Support Activities in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of regional economic trends, offering valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for sustainable growth in these pivotal sectors.

References

- Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.
- Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.
- Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a. The Viability Of The Mountainous Region In Northeastern Romania Is Supported By The Sectors Of Wholesale And Retail Trade, As Well As The Repair Of Motor Vehicles And Motorcycles. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021b. Organizational Dynamics In Mountainous Regions: Navigating Challenges And Fostering Sustainable Development. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021c. Theoretical Framework For Examining Entrepreneurship In Mountainous Regions. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021d. The Current Landscape Of Mountain Entrepreneurship In Europe: An In-Depth Analysis. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021e. Entrepreneurship In The Romanian Mountains: Exploring Probiotic Properties In Vegetable Products. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 2/2021

- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021f. Predictive Analysis Of Food And Service-Centric Entrepreneurship In Mountainous Regions: Insights From Agritourism. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021g. Food And Services Sectors In Central And Eastern European Countries. Case Study Of Mountain Area. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021h. Romanian Mountain Entrepreneurs Of Dairy And Beekeeping Products: A Biotic Perspective. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a. Investigating Science, Technology, And Research Infrastructure In The European Mountainous Region: A Comprehensive Analysis From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022b. Hospitality And Culinary Service Operations In European Mountainous Regions From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022c. Economic Analysis Of Financial, Insurance, And Real Estate Activities In European Mountainous Regions From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022d. Exploring Financial And Insurance Activities, Real Estate Operations In The Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022e. Evolution Of The Construction Sector In Romanian Mountain Macroregions From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022
- Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022f. Exploring Sector-Specific Progress In Wholesale And Retail Trade, Motor Vehicle, And Motorcycle Repair In The

Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022g. Investigating Sector-Specific Advancements In Transportation And Storage In The Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022h. Exploring Sector-Specific Advancements In Accommodation And Food Service Activities Within The Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018: An Academic Inquiry. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021a. Considerations Regarding The Influence Of Entropy In Organizations. A Mountain View. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021b. Online Learning In The Pandemic Era: A Statistical Analysis Of Course Trends. A Mountain Approach. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021c. Navigating Entropy: The Influence Of Organizational Culture. A Mountain Perspective. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021d. Deciphering Organizations And Entropy - A Mountain Context. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021e. World Contexts Of Entrepreneurship, As Support For Specific Economic Contexts Of Mountain Investments. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021f. Entrepreneurial Endeavors In The Romanian Mountains: Industry, Construction, And Services. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021g. Professional, Scientific And Technical, Administrative And Support Of The Romanian Mountain Activities. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021h. Education, Human Health And Social Assistance Activities Of The Romanian Mountain Activities. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022a. Statistical Overview Of Information And Communication Sector Advancements In The Romanian Mountain Region (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022b. An In-Depth Statistical Analysis Of Financial And Insurance Activities, Real Estate Developments In The Romanian Mountain Area: A Decadal Perspective (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022c. A Decade In Review: Evolution Of Education, Human Health, And Social Assistance Sectors In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022d. Ten Years Of Cultural Flourish: Developments In The Arts, Entertainment, Recreation Sectors, And Other Service Activities In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022e. Entrepreneurial Resilience In The Romanian Mountain Region: A Decade Of Growth And Challenges For Active Enterprises (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022f. A Tale Of Resilience: An Analysis Of Dissolved And Newly Established Enterprises In The Romanian Mountain Sector Surviving Until 2018. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022g. Navigating Economic Peaks: A Comprehensive Analysis Of Employment Trends In The Population Of

PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (1/2022)

Active Enterprises In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022h. Employment Horizons: An In-Depth Examination Of Employability In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2022)

Covaci-Sterpu. Rapoarte de cercetare doctorală. Universitatea din Oradea. European Commission (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151> (Accessed: 14 June 2021)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665> (Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)

PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (1/2022)